

Determination of thiram (tetramethylene thiuram disulphide), in presence of zineb (zinc bis ethylene dithiocarbamate), maneb (manganese bis ethylene dithiocarbamate), nabam (disodium bis ethylene dithiocarbamate), vapam (sodium monomethyl dithiocarbamate), ziram (zinc dimethyl dithiocarbamate) and ferbam (ferric dimethyl dithiocarbamate): Interference of some of the common reagents like zineb, maneb, nabam, vapam, ferbam and ziram which are mostly used as pesticides has been studied. Nabam, zineb, maneb and vapam formed blue coloured complexes in the aqueous phase which were extractable into isobutyl methyl ketone, i.e. on boiling only, whereas thiram formed yellow coloured complex which was extractable in isobutyl methyl ketone in cold. The following compounds (mg amounts in parentheses) did not interfere in the determination of thiram (400 µg) in 5 ml of the final solution: nabam (1), zineb (1), maneb (1) and vapam (0.5). Ziram and ferbam, if present, interfered.

Simultaneous determination of thiram and zineb: Synthetic mixtures of thiram and zineb in various proportions were prepared. Taking advantage of the colour of the molybdenum-thiram (yellow) and molybdenum-zineb (blue), thiram and zineb can be determined simultaneously. Binary mixture was dissolved in 0.1N NaOH and boiled to dissolve thiram. To this solution, appropriate amounts of 2M H₂SO₄ and 2% sodium molybdate solution were added, yellow coloured complex formed by thiram with sodium molybdate in cold was extractable into isobutyl methyl ketone whereas blue coloured complex of zineb-molybdenum was not extractable in cold. So aqueous phase was boiled for 5–7 min, then cooled and extracted with isobutyl methyl ketone. The absorbance of the extracts were measured at 420 nm for thiram-molybdenum complex and at 670 nm for zineb-molybdenum complex and the amount of thiram and ziram were determined from their respective calibration curves.

Similarly, simultaneous determination of thiram and maneb, thiram and nabam, thiram and vapam were possible (Table 1).

TABLE 1—SIMULTANEOUS DETERMINATION OF ZINEB AND THIRAM FROM SYNTHETIC MIXTURES

Amount taken (µg)		Amount found (µg)		Error (%)	
Zineb	Thiram	Zineb	Thiram	Zineb	Thiram
20	50	19.75	49.65	-1.25	-0.70
40	100	39.75	99.40	-0.63	-0.60
60	150	59.50	149.0	-0.84	-0.67
80	200	79.50	201.0	-0.63	+0.50

The wide applicability of the method was tested by the satisfactory analysis of a variety of synthetic samples containing thiram upto 400 µg in the aliquot. The method is quite selective for thiram determination in the presence of zineb, maneb, nabam and vapam. The proposed method is quite simple and rapid as it takes less than 15 min for thiram determination after preparation of thiram solution. It is one of the sensitive methods available for thiram

determination and could be used in the analysis of commercial samples and for residual analysis of thiram from various food stuff.

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Extractive Determination of Copper(II) Present in some Biological Samples with Lead Salt of Dipropylthiocarbamate in Chloroform by Standard Addition Method

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It is evident from the literature that no work on the extraction of copper(II) with dipropylthiocarbamate has been reported. The present paper describes a method of extractive estimation of copper(II) from some biological samples by standard addition method using lead dipropylthiocarbamate in chloroform as extractant.

Experimental

Elco pH meter, Spectronic-20 (Bausch and Lomb) and Shimadzu recording spectrophotometer were used. Chemicals used were of A.R. grade, otherwise specified. Commercial grade chloroform was purified¹ and distilled. The fraction collected at 60–81° was used as diluent for the extraction.

To a mixture of potassium nitrate solution (10% ; 5 ml) and lead acetate solution (0.05 g in 10 ml water), was added dipropylthiocarbamate (0.1 g) followed by chloroform (100 ml). The mixture was shaken for 10 min and allowed to equilibrate. The chloroform layer was collected and diluted upto 250 ml with chloroform. Required amount of pentahydrated copper sulphate was dissolved in water and standardised. The desired metal ion concentration was prepared from this solution.

The biological samples such as cabbage, lady's finger, bean, cauliflower and carrot were procured from local market. Each sample was cleaned and dried in an air-oven (90–100°) and subsequently dry-ashed in a muffle furnace (500–550°). Sample of ash (1.0 g) was dissolved in aqua regia and heated to dryness. Heating to dryness was repeated till the removal of all nitrate ions. It was diluted with 2 M HCl and filtered. The residue was thoroughly washed, and the washings and filtrate were diluted to 100 ml.

Eight systems were prepared each of which containing 1.0 mg of copper(II) and 5 ml of citric acid solution (10%). The pH of these systems were adjusted from 1 to 9. The volume of each system was kept constant (10 ml) with respective pH water. Copper(II) was extracted from each system with 5 ml of dipropylthiocarbamate solution in chloroform. After drying, the absorbance of each extract was measured at 435 nm against lead dipropylthiocarbamate in chloroform.

Five systems were prepared containing constant amount of unknown and a known amount (0, 2, 4, 6 and 8 µg) of copper(II). To each system citric acid solution (5 ml; 10%) was added. The pH of the systems was adjusted to 2 and the volume kept constant (20 ml). Copper was extracted from each system with chloroform solution of lead dipropylthiocarbamate (2 × 5 ml). The absorbance of each extract was measured at 435 nm against reagent blank treated similarly after drying.

Results and Discussion

The extraction of copper was observed to be maximum and remained practically constant between 1 and 3 pH. For further studies, experiments were carried out at pH 2.

The absorbances of different unknown ash solutions of cabbage, cauliflower, lady's finger, carrot and bean (long type) were found to be 0.102, 0.119, 0.140, 0.155, 0.186 respectively. Addition of 2, 4, 6 and 8 µg of copper showed very good linear relationship between the absorbances and concentrations. The results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—EXTRACTIVE ESTIMATION OF COPPER BY STANDARD ADDITION METHOD AND DITHIZONE METHOD

Samples	Copper found per 100 g of sample	
	By standard addition method*	By dithizone method**
	µg	µg
Cabbage (<i>Brassica oleracea</i> var. capitata)	13.5 ± 0.4	13.3
Cauliflower (<i>Brassica oleracea</i> var. botrytis)	32.0 ± 1.0	26.7
Carrot (<i>Daucus carota</i>)	44.6 ± 0.5	40.9
Lady's finger (<i>Ambelmoschus esculentus</i>)	58.0 ± 1.0	61.5
Bean, long type (<i>Canavalia gladiata</i>)	101.9 ± 0.4	99.0

*Results on extractive estimation of copper from biological samples by standard addition method¹.

**Extractive determination of the metal with dithizone³

It is observed that the results are in good agreement with each other. It is also revealed that lady's finger and bean have high copper content. This amount of copper does not affect the health. These studies also throw some light on the amount of copper we consume per day per meal along with the vegetables.

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